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ABSTRACT

This document, produced as part of the EU Horizon 2020 PlasticsFatE project (Deliverable D2.3, Annex III), provides comprehensive guidance on best practices and method validation for the detection and quantification of microplastics (MPs) and nanoplastics (NPs) in diverse matrices. It emphasizes the critical importance of integrating quality assurance (QA) and quality control (QC) principles. Given the heterogeneity of analytical techniques and sample types, the document outlines tailored strategies for method development and in-house validation, including protocols for evaluating performance parameters such as accuracy, precision, trueness, limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantification (LOQ), selectivity, and robustness.

Special attention is given to the validation of both number- and mass-based quantification methods, as well as particle sizing techniques, highlighting the need for flexible and purpose-driven validation frameworks. The guide also addresses error detection via different types of QC samples (e.g., blanks and spikes), and the estimation of measurement uncertainty using top-down and bottom-up approaches. In addition, it covers the validation of software tools used in data analysis and provides detailed recommendations for transparent result reporting.

The aim of this document is to improve reproducibility, harmonization, and scientific integrity in MNPs research, supporting regulatory relevance and risk assessment.

Annex III: Best Practices and Method Validation: A guide for scientists investigating the occurrence of microplastics (MPs) and nanoplastics (NPs)

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III.1. Introduction

The diverse exposure to various polymer materials highlights the need for additional careful planning and execution in analytical micro- and nanoplastics research. The foundation of the research should be established in the study design, with clear goals and methods that align with the intended outcomes. Research activities on micro- and nanoplastics have been criticized for lacking proper data quality² and often for lacking realism³. Therefore, proper sampling and sample preparation protocols, as well as the selection of suitable detection and quantification methods, should be carefully planned and executed, with quality assurance/quality control (QC/QA) protocols upheld as a top priority.

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² Albert A. Koelmans et al., "Microplastics in Freshwaters and Drinking Water: Critical Review and Assessment of Data Quality," *Water Research* 155 (2019): 410–22, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2019.02.054>

³ Judith S. Weis and Karl H. Palmquist, "Reality Check: Experimental Studies on Microplastics Lack Realism," *Applied Sciences* 11, no. 18 (2021): 8529, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11188529>

The OECD principles of "Good Laboratory Practice" (GLP) define a set of rules and criteria under which non-clinical health and environmental safety studies are planned, performed, monitored, recorded, reported, and archived⁴. Thus, implementing consistent QA/QC procedures should be considered early and maintained throughout the study process. This includes study design, sampling, sample preparation, microplastics/nanoplastics (MPs/NPs) extraction, analysis, method validation, and reporting. Proper practices enhance the reliability and comparability of data on MNPs. Although there are many facets to QA/QC in MNPs analysis, one of the most critical elements is the laboratory working environment. This document emphasizes that aspect, focusing on proper method validation and the accurate reporting of the results.

III.2. The Role of Quality Assurance (QA) and Quality Control (QC) in MNPs Research

Research's high standards and integrity can only be upheld if adequate Quality Assurance (QA) and Quality Control (QC) practices are followed. This is especially crucial and challenging in microplastics research, where the widespread occurrence of plastics and the lack of harmonized or standardized detection and quantification methods can lead to unreliable results. By definition, QA focuses on planning and prevention, taking proactive steps to establish procedures and protocols that ensure processes yield consistent, reliable outcomes. In contrast, QC involves regular, reactive evaluations to identify and correct discrepancies in the final output, ensuring that results meet established standards. While QA sets the foundation for quality, QC verifies whether the outcome meets expectations:

- **Quality assurance** in MNPs research ensures that the entire process — from study design to data interpretation — yields reliable, reproducible, and credible results. QA prevents errors by implementing protocols and procedures, such as Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs), which ensure that all processes are conducted according to predefined quality standards.
- **Quality control** in MNPs research is essential to maintain the accuracy, reliability, and reproducibility of results, thus safeguarding data integrity. Proper guidance in sample collection and handling procedures is critical to preventing contamination, a primary concern in MNP research. The analysis of QC samples enables the detection and correction of errors, while thorough documentation and validation of procedures confirm the suitability of methods and the accuracy of results. Each aspect of the QC procedures is further detailed below.

III.3. Error Detection, Correction – Quality Control samples

Quality control samples ensure that analytical detection and quantification methods provide accurate and reliable results, particularly in complex matrices such as food, air, personal care products, or biota. They allow for the correction of systematic and random errors. Generally, we can distinguish three types of QC samples: matrix blank samples, spiked samples, and "real" matrix blanks, each described in more detail below:

- **spiked samples** represent samples with a known quantity of the target of interest, such as MNPs, that has been added to the sample. These types of samples are used in method development and validation to assess method performance.
- **matrix blank samples** contain the same type of matrix as the sample of interest but without the target of interest (MNPs). The purpose of this control sample is to identify background contamination that originates from the matrix.

⁴ <https://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/testing/overview-of-good-laboratory-practice.htm>

- **analytical blank samples** represent samples that contain solvents, reagents, and any other materials used during sample handling, preparation, and analysis. This allows for the correction of contamination introduced by solvents, glassware, or laboratory processes.

III.4. Analytical Method Validation

This guideline aims to ensure the compliance of the in-house validations with international standards. This document is based on the **IUPAC** "Harmonised Guidelines for Single-Laboratory Validation of Analytical Methods", the **Eurachem** Guide "Fitness for Purpose of Analytical Methods", and the **European Commission** Decision 2002/657/EC on the reliability of methods for residues and contaminants in food of animal origin. The analytical techniques used for detecting and quantifying microplastics are very diverse; therefore, a dynamic approach to method validation may be required. This may involve poorly defined endpoints and, as such, may not follow traditional assumptions (*e.g.*, linearity). It may also require the validator to perform iterative method validations under different conditions, customise the methods for specific uses, and combine multiple methods for different matrices. As such, we propose this report be maintained as a living document, which will be refined and adjusted based on experience of what works and what is not applicable for different methods and method combinations in terms of the validation approach.

Good method validations are not *ad hoc* exercises but examine a candidate method designed for a certain purpose against previously defined parameters with set minimum performance criteria described in detail in the validation plan. These performance criteria must be achieved to ascertain that the proposed method fits-the-purpose. Therefore, agreeing on such minimum performance criteria is necessary. Another requirement for method validation procedures includes applying conditions that reflect the situation in the later analysis (under routine conditions). The prime objective of method validation is not only to achieve results under the best-case scenario but to reflect the performance that can be expected during the future use of the method under the conditions stipulated in the **standard operating procedure (SOP)**.

The guidelines presented here are specifically designed to apply to quantitative analyses. However, where there is some ambiguity around the measurand (the physical quantity or property which is measured) or where only a constituent part of the total analyte is required (*e.g.*, the bioavailable fraction), clarification and detailed specification of the measurand that is being validated will be necessary. Additionally, for qualitative or semi-quantitative methods, such as microscopy analysis of MPs, some aspects of this document will not be applicable or will require further modification (*e.g.*, assumptions around linearity or the calculation of measurement trueness). Methods that have a subjective component (*e.g.*, microscopy) and where there is a lack of available international guidelines/standards for non-quantitative methods will require careful consideration to maximise the effectiveness of the approach.

III.4.1. Method validation parameters

Standardised methods for determining MPs in different complex matrices must undergo in-house method validation. Before the validation plan can be finalised, a description of the method procedure (or SOP) is required. Briefly, this SOP should document all the essential parts of the method, such as the description of the measurand, type of samples, method parameters, sample preparation and data evaluation, and a determination of the measurement uncertainty.

A **validation plan** is a document that includes all headings for the method performance parameters, the performance criteria and a proposed experimental setup. It must be justified whenever parameters are irrelevant to a particular method. The **method performance parameters** are defined in Table 1 and commented on in the following sections.

Table 1. Analytical method performance parameters

Performance parameter	Definition
Accuracy	The closeness of agreement between a test result and the accepted reference value.
Between-run variation	Run-to-run standard deviation corrected for repeatability, e.g. by ANOVA. Between-run variation and repeatability are combined to obtain the intermediate precision.
Bias	The difference between the expectation of a test result and an expected reference value (describes the systematic error).
Confirmatory method	A method that provides full or complementary information enabling the substance to be unequivocally identified and, if necessary, quantified at the level of interest (Decision 657/2002/EC). For example, in the case of particle size analysis, this can be understood as a method that is used to obtain a definitive result of the (average) particle size of a particulate material.
Intermediate precision	A measure of precision under a defined set of conditions. An intermediate between reproducibility conditions and Repeatability conditions (ISO 5725).
Limit of detection (LOD, method)	The LOD is the lowest quantity of a substance that can be distinguished from the absence of that substance (in a spiked blank matrix sample) with a stated confidence interval. The LOD is a measured quantity value obtained by a given measurement procedure, for which the probability of falsely claiming the absence of a component in a material is β , given a probability α of falsely claiming its presence (ISO/IEC Guide 99:2007).
Limit of quantification (LOQ, method):	The lowest concentration of a substance that can be quantified in a spiked blank matrix sample with an acceptable (depending on the method and intended use of results) level of repeatability, precision and trueness. The LOQ is also the lowest concentration at which the performance of a method or measurement system is acceptable for a specified use.
Linearity	The linearity of an analytical procedure is its ability (within a given range) to obtain test results which are directly proportional to each other (with an R^2 of >0.999).
Mass concentration	Is a measure of the amount of a substance (mass) present in a given volume of space. Typically expressed in units such as grams per litre (g/L), or milligrams per litre (mg/L).
Measurement uncertainty (u)	Parameter, associated with a measurement result, characterises the dispersion of the values that could reasonably be attributed to the measurand.
Number concentration	Number of particles (or number of particles in a certain size class) per volume or mass of substance.
Precision	The closeness of agreement between independent test results obtained under stipulated conditions (ISO 5725-1).
Qualitative method	A method that identifies substances based on chemical, biological or physical properties; method of analysis whose response is either the presence or absence of the substance detected, or indirectly a certain amount of substance in a certain amount of sample. Most qualitative methods are, or can be made, at least 'semi-quantitative' to provide rough estimates of the amount of substance present.
Quantitative method	A method that estimates the amount of substance present in the test sample, expressed as a numerical value in appropriate units, with trueness and Precision that are fit-for-purpose.
Recovery	The ability to measure or recover a known amount of substance from fortified samples over the range of quantitation (ISO 21572:2004).

Repeatability	The precision under repeatability conditions, i.e., where independent test results are obtained with the same method on identical test items in the same laboratory using the same equipment within short time intervals (ISO 5725).
Reproducibility	The precision under reproducibility conditions, i.e., independent test results are obtained with the same method on different test items in different laboratories using different equipment (ISO 5725).
Resolution	The smallest interval measurable by a microscope or other scientific instrument.
Robustness	The extent to which slight deviations from the measurement protocol influence the result.
Screening method	A method used to detect the presence of a substance or class of substances at the level of interest specified. These methods have the capability for a high sample throughput and are used to sift large numbers of samples for potential non-compliant results. They are specifically designed to avoid false compliant results (Decision 657/2002/EC). In the case of particle size analysis, this can be understood as a method that is used to obtain a first estimate of the (average) particle size of a particulate material.
Selectivity	The ability of a method to determine accurately and selectively the substance of interest in the presence of other components in a sample matrix under the stated conditions of the test.
Sensitivity	The smallest amount of difference in analyte or matrix quantity that will change an instrument's readings.
Trueness	The closeness of agreement between the average value obtained from a large set of test results and an accepted reference value (ISO 5725).
Verification	The confirmation by examination and provision of the objective evidence that specified requirements for performance of a method have been fulfilled by an individual laboratory. The means used to demonstrate that the method functions (without adaption) in the user's laboratory on matrices not included in the original validation.
Working range	The range of concentration (number or mass) can be adequately determined by the instrument, where the instrument provides a useful signal related to the substance's concentration.

It is crucial to note that when conducting particulate analysis, both accurate quantification and reliable estimation of microplastic particle size are critical parameters. Therefore, in addition to the parameters mentioned in the Table 1, it is necessary to validate the Limit of Detection for size (LOD_{size}) and the working size range for analytical techniques capable of determining size (further elaborated in the following sections).

The description of the validation parameters, ways of their determination as well as validation results and judgement of the method fit-of-purpose are summarised in the **validation report**.

Depending on the method's purpose, different method performance parameters from Table 1 must be determined, as not all will necessarily be applicable or even possible. If some of the performance parameters do not make sense in the method context, this must be justified in the validation plan and report. The **Inter-laboratory Comparison** studies tackle the parameter reproducibility and do not form part of the in-house validations.

Linearity

Linearity defines the ability of a method to obtain test results proportional to the value of the measurand/property of interest. Typically, a calibration curve is created across the range of the analytical procedure. The calibration should be valid over a range that is greater than the expected value, and the calibration levels should preferably be distributed evenly over the range of interest. A

minimum of 5 concentrations is recommended. The calibration levels should be measured in a random order, not including blanks, and should consist of 2 values above and below the expected range. Usually, the calibration response is linear, although it does not have to be linear for a method to be effective, providing an appropriate calibration function is established. The performance criteria for assessing linearity should be laid down in the validation plan. Linearity should be initially assessed by visual inspection of the plotted data followed by considering different parameters/statistical measures, *e.g.*, analysis of the residuals, response factors, correlation coefficient, significance test of the slope and intercept. The validation report details the results of the relevant parameters/statistical measures.

The linearity of a method must be characterised to establish the calibration regime for future uses. If the same calibration curve is to be used for a long period, it has to be shown that calibration curves remain – within the uncertainty of the method – valid for the chosen time. This requires comparing several calibration curves generated over a comparable period, for example, at the beginning and end of experimental acquisition.

If the concept of linearity is not applicable due to the measurement principle, this should be explained in the validation plan and report. This particularly applies to the size aspect of particle size analysis techniques, where calibration is unnecessary, unlike the quantity aspect.

Working range

The working range of an analytical method is the interval between the upper and lower levels, including these levels, at which the analytical procedure provides an acceptable degree of linearity, trueness and precision when applied to samples containing amounts of substance or property levels within or at the extremes of the specified range of the analytical procedure. Typically, extrapolations beyond the calibrated range are not acceptable.

The working range may depend on a combination of different properties for methods based on physical principles. Therefore, different approaches for establishing the working range will need to be applied depending on the physical properties of measurand.

Sensitivity

The sensitivity of an analytical method is the capability of the method to discriminate small differences in the concentration of mass of the test analyte. In practical terms, sensitivity is the slope of the calibration curve that is obtained by plotting the response against the analyte concentration or mass.

Limit of detection and limit of quantification

Two different cases can be distinguished when dealing with detection limits: firstly, the number or mass concentration of the MPs. Secondly, the minimum and maximum MPs size mark the lower and higher end of the working range for the specific method.

Instrumental LOD and LOQ of number or mass concentration

There are three different methods to determine and calculate the LOD and LOQ for instruments that relate the number or mass of particles to a collective signal coming from the sample, *i.e.*, via the calibration curve, via the signal-to-noise ratio or via the standard deviation for the matrix blank samples. While the first two methods are more applicable with mass-based techniques (*e.g.*, Py-GCMS), the latter method is applicable when the number-based concentration is determined. The

specific method used to determine the LOD and LOQ should be documented in the validation plan and report. In the validation plan, an appropriate minimum number of particles to be analysed should be specified.

Determining the LOD and LOQ from the calibration curve

This approach can be applicable even if a matrix blank sample or a spiked sample that closely resembles it is not available. The LOD and LOQ for the instrumental part of the method can be estimated automatically from the calibration curve obtained with matrix-free suspensions according to the Equations (1) and (2), respectively.

$$LOD = \frac{3 \times SD}{b} \quad (1)$$

$$LOQ = \frac{10 \times SD}{b} \quad (2)$$

where: b is the slope of the regression line, and SD is the Standard Deviation.

Note that this approach requires that the variability of measurements of standards is very similar (ideally the same) to the variability of the measurement of real samples. Too optimistic values for LOD and LOQ will be obtained if the variability of the measurement of standards is significantly lower than those of real samples.

Determining the LOD and LOQ from the signal-to-noise ratio

This approach can be used for methods that demonstrate baseline noise. The signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) shall be determined by comparing measured signals from samples with known low concentrations of substance with those of blank matrix samples, thus establishing the minimum limit at which the substance can be reliably detected. Each measurement must represent a complete and independent application of the method, including sample preparation steps. A S/N ratio of 3 corresponds to the LOD, and 10 corresponds to the LOQ.

Determining the LOD and LOQ from a blank matrix sample or a sample with a concentration close to the LOD/LOQ value (Method of choice for MPs)

A matrix blank sample that resembles the real matrix blank should be available or prepared as closely as possible (*i.e.*, a low spiked matrix or a material with a low substance content). If such a blank sample is not available, a "method" blank sample could be substituted, mimicking all the analysis conditions but without the matrix. Another alternative is to use the sample with the lowest substance concentration available. Three independent subsamples should be analysed for a rough estimation. At least 6 independent subsamples shall be analysed for a more precise determination of the LOD and LOQ as provided by Equations (3) and (4). The standard deviation of the results is calculated. If the standard deviation is taken in analytical units (e.g., diameter, number counting) rather than a signal, the expression s/b should be replaced by the standard deviation of the results in analytical units (s).

$$LOD = \frac{3 \times SD}{b} \quad (3)$$

$$LOD = \frac{10 \times SD}{b} \quad (4)$$

where b is the slope of the calibration curve; for methods not applying a calibration curve such as the counting of particles, b is equal 1, and SD is the standard deviation of the measurements.

Size LOD (LOD_{size}) and dynamic range

It is also important to determine the smallest and largest particle size that can be reliably detected or quantified. As the characterisation of a potential MP's contamination is usually based on data from different techniques, it is crucial that realistic working ranges are known. The size detection limit LOD_{size} depends on the ability of the instrument to distinguish the signal of an MP from the background noise. In principle, a similar approach using the $3 \times SD$ and $10 \times SD$ criteria (see Equations (3) and (4)).

Certain methods also have a LOD_{size} depending on, e.g., the possibility to acquire images at a certain magnification. In addition, D_{max} and LOD_{size} may also be related if the dynamic range of the method is limited (e.g. in microscopy or in centrifugal liquid sedimentation, one cannot at the same time measure very small and very large particles).

Trueness

Trueness is an expression of how close the mean of an infinite number of results (produced by the method) is to a reference value. In practice, trueness is assessed by estimating the magnitude of the **experimental bias** and by determining if it is statistically significant. This is done by comparing the mean of the results to an appropriate reference value. Bias is typically determined using one of three methods (listing is in the order of preference):

- Analysis of Certified Reference Materials (CRMs)
- Recovery experiments using spiked samples
- Comparing the new method with another reference method.

Performance criteria for the estimation of trueness must be stated in the method validation plan. If these criteria are not met in the trueness check, then the method should be further optimised. The application of these approaches is elaborated below.

Analysis of a Certified Reference Material (CRM)

Whenever available, CRMs are the preferred option for trueness assessment. CRMs in trueness experiments are materials which come with one or more relevant certified property values (e.g. consisting of the substance(s) of interest present in a matrix at a specific concentration level, size). The ideal **reference material** (RM) should have property values close to those of the sample of interest. It is also important to note that an RM should only be used for one purpose during validation studies. For example, a material used for calibration shall not be used to evaluate bias.

Usually, 6 replicate analyses of the (C)RM have to be carried out. Each replicate analysis must represent a complete and independent application of the method, including sample preparation steps. The bias that describes the systematic error is calculated using Equation (5) or (6), when the relative bias value is reported.

$$Bias = C - C_{ref} \quad (5)$$

$$Relative\ Bias\ [\%] = \frac{C - C_{ref}}{C_{ref}} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

where C represents the mean concentration determined for the CRM, and C_{ref} is a certified value of the CRM.

Alternatively, values from the performed ILC studies can be used in the same way to estimate trueness. The assigned value (often a **"consensus" value**) is used instead of the certified value of the CRM. The uncertainty of the assigned value must be estimated if not provided by the ILC organisers. Assessment of the statistical significance of the experimental bias is based on the estimation of the measurement uncertainty described in the section "Measurement uncertainty".

Recovery evaluation using spiked samples

In the absence of CRMs, recovery studies may be used to give an indication of the likely level of bias. This involves adding a known amount of substance to a known amount of matrix, which may or may not contain the substance. If the amount of added substance and the amount of matrix are accurately measured, and if the substance is carefully dispersed into the matrix, then the increase in substance content in the matrix will be accurately known and can be used as a reference value. In addition, the choice between particle-based and mass-based detection methods should be carefully considered, as the spiking strategy and the amount used must align with the requirements of the selected technique. Care shall be taken to introduce the substance in such a way that it resembles the substance naturally present in the sample as closely as possible and minimises variability due to heterogeneity. This determination is often combined with the determination of repeatability. Each replicate analysis must represent a complete and independent application of the method, including sample preparation steps. A blank matrix sample is also analysed. The evaluation is similar to using CRMs, with the assigned value being the spiking level. The uncertainty for the spike will usually be negligible compared to the Precision.

This method assesses the recovery of the added spike, relative spike recovery (R') usually expressed in per cent (Equation (7)). The results are interpreted by comparing the known amount added (X_{spike}) with the difference between the results obtained with (C') and without (C) addition for each sample matrix separately. The associated bias value is calculated according to the Equation (8).

$$\% R' = \frac{C' - C}{X_{spike}} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

$$Bias = X_{spike} - (C' - C) \quad (8)$$

The bias may be checked for statistical significance in order to decide on the future correction of results. If bias is statistically significant, preferably, bias should be corrected by a correction factor rather than included in the uncertainty budget to minimise the combined uncertainty. If the bias is not statistically significant, the inclusion of its contribution in the uncertainty budget is also possible.

When no corresponding blank matrix sample is available, a sample containing the substance (real sample) may be spiked at a given concentration level. The blank sample is, therefore, replaced by the real sample. The same procedures as described in this chapter can then be applied.

Use of a reference method

In this approach, results from a reference method (a method currently in routine use) are used and assigned as the reference values. If one method would be considered as a reference with a higher intrinsic trueness, other methods under validation could be related to that "reference" method. However, in particle analysis, measurands are mostly method-defined, and it has to be critically analysed to determine if the measurands of the two methods are comparable to justify the application of the reference method concept. Samples that cover the full range of analyte concentrations/property values as specified in the method scope shall be selected. At least 6 replicate analyses shall be performed on each single sample with both methods. The replicates are spread over different days depending on repeatability and day-to-day variation for both methods. Each replicate analysis must represent a complete and independent application of the method, including sample preparation steps. The ratio of method responses between the tested methods (R_m) expressed in percentage and the associated bias are calculated according to the Equations (9) and (10), respectively.

$$R_m[\%] = \frac{C_1}{C_2} \times 100 \quad (9)$$

$$Bias = |C_2 - C_1| \quad (10)$$

where C_1 represents the mean result obtained with the method to be validated and C_2 is the mean result obtained with the standard or reference method.

Assessment of the statistical significance of the experimental bias is based on the estimate of the measurement uncertainty described in the section "Measurement uncertainty". During the evaluation of the in-house validation results at the project level, an assessment of results from different methods for identical materials could be made that would give more insight into potential method biases.

Selectivity

Selectivity is the ability of an analytical method to differentiate and quantify a substance in the presence of other substances/components in the sample. Potentially interfering substances (i.e. particles, matrix) should already have been identified during method development and optimisation. The conclusions regarding the selectivity of the chosen method should also be based on the literature data and expert knowledge. If any doubt of the presence of interferences arises, confirmatory tests shall be performed. The analysis of true positives can do this. The analyst has to decide how much supporting evidence is necessary (taking into account time and costs) to have sufficient confidence in the confirmation of identity arising from the method. Important to note that serious interferences need to be eliminated, but minor effects can be tolerated and included in the uncertainty budget.

In the case of environmental samples and consumer products, two different scenarios need to be addressed: the selectivity against matrix constituents and the selectivity against other types of MPs. Representative pictures (diagrams, photographs) should be part of the validation report.

Precision

Precision may be considered at three levels: repeatability, intermediate precision (IP), and reproducibility. In this document, only repeatability and IP are considered. The inter-laboratory validation study will tackle parameter reproducibility and, hence, does not form part of the in-house validations.

Repeatability

Analysis of various subsamples determines repeatability expressed as standard deviation. The number of degrees of freedom for the SD should be at least 9. This is achieved by analysing 6 subsamples in one run or by e.g. analysing three subsamples each on five different days.

Intermediate precision (within-laboratory reproducibility)

IP studies are carried out according to ISO 5725-3 Accuracy (trueness and precision) of measurement methods and results⁵. In order to estimate IP, the analytical method can be tested on different days, by different analysts, on different equipment and/or under different calibrations. The variation of at least one of these factors has to be investigated.

The IP, such as day-to-day variation, is tested by using a nested design, as prescribed by ISO 5725-3. An example of a simple nested design for the evaluation of time-different IP for a single typical sample is shown in Figure 1. Each day, 3 replicate analyses are made under repeatability conditions ($n = 3$) for a minimum number of 5 days ($p \geq 5$). Another option could be 6 replicate analyses made under repeatability conditions ($n = 6$) on 3 different days ($p \geq 3$). Each replicate analysis must represent a complete and independent application of the method, including sample preparation steps. For test materials, the samples have to be tested "as is"; for the environmental, biological and product matrices, more than one concentration or size level could be tested if fortified test samples can be prepared.

The data obtained according to Figure 1's setup are analysed by means of an analysis of variance (ANOVA), which yields repeatability as "within group" standard deviation and day-to-day variation as "between group" standard deviation.

⁵ <https://www.nen.nl/en/iso-5725-3-2023-en-312606>

Figure 1. Nested design for the evaluation of time-different IP. (M1 is matrix 1, C1 is concentration level 1, R1 is replicate 1, p = number of days).

The mean of squares between days are calculated (MS_{day}), as well as those between replicates (MS_r), using the formulas given in Table 2.

Table 2. Equations to calculate MS_{day} and MS_r

Sources of variability	MS	Variance estimated
Days	$MS_{day} = \frac{n \sum (\bar{x}_i - \bar{x})^2}{p - 1}$	$MS_{day} = s_r^2 + n * s_{day}^2$
Replicates	$MS_r = \frac{\sum \sum (\bar{x}_{ij} - \bar{x}_i)^2}{p(n - 1)}$	$MS_r = s_r^2$

From these mean of square values, the following variance components are estimated: s_r^2 and s_{day}^2 as estimates of the repeatability variance and between-day variance. The time-different IP, $s_{I(T)}^2$, is then calculated as:

$$s_{I(T)}^2 = s_r^2 + s_{day}^2 \quad (11)$$

This setup of the experiments ($n = 3$, $p = 5$) should be identical for all method validations to allow comparability of all in-house validation results in the project. Note that the repeatability/intermediate precision experiment can also be used for the assessment of trueness if the samples selected fulfil the requirements for the trueness experiment.

Robustness

During a robustness test, small but deliberate changes are made to the method variables, and the effect on the method performance is studied. The testing of the robustness may preferably follow

the method development. The method variables selected shall be based on the observations made during method development and shall represent the critical method variables that have the most influence on the method performance or method result. For each method variable, upper and lower limits, in general, equally distributed around the nominal value, have to be defined in the validation protocol. These upper and lower limits have to represent the natural variability that can be expected if a population of laboratories carries out the method. Criteria for these responses must be defined in the validation protocol to evaluate the robustness of a response or a series of responses. Examples of typical method variables for a method based on chemical principles are reaction times, concentrations of reagents, pH, temperature, flow rates and background concentration.

Stability of samples

The stability of samples during analysis (including sample preparation) is usually checked during method development. When samples are proven not to be stable, the corresponding SOP should stress the necessity of taking the measurements as soon as possible after preparation or in any way within the stability time frame. Apart from stability during the whole analysis, the stability of samples during the actual measurement could be in focus, such as thermal or cooling degradation sensitivity or analyte degradation due to acidic or basic conditions during sample digestion.

Measurement uncertainty

For estimating measurement uncertainties, a top-down approach based on method performance can be applied as a stand-alone method or in combination with bottom-up uncertainty budgets. Validation data of a method can be used by the laboratory that uses the method for routine analyses to make an uncertainty statement. It is based on the fact that the combined influence of many effects is quantified simultaneously by estimating repeatability, IP and trueness. The lab has to show that it is sufficiently proficient. Therefore, it is crucial that the method is under control at the time of the measurement, i.e. that all performance tests and performance qualifications for the method are fulfilled. If this is not the case, the data obtained during method validation will not provide a reliable uncertainty estimate and, therefore, cannot be used for the individual measurement. Measurement uncertainty of a result consists of three contributions, namely:

- 1) Standard or relative uncertainty due to repeatability (s_r or u_r);
- 2) Standard or relative uncertainty due to day-to-day variations (s_{day} or u_{day}) and
- 3) Standard or relative uncertainty due to trueness (s_t or u_t).

The standard measurement uncertainty u_x associated with an individual measurement result x is then estimated by combining the individual uncertainty sources using the root sum of squares approach:

$$u_x = \sqrt{s_r^2 + s_{day}^2 + s_t^2} \quad (12)$$

The relative measurement uncertainty is calculated as follows:

$$u_x = x \sqrt{u_r^2 + u_{day}^2 + u_t^2} \quad (13)$$

For quantitative measurements, the standard measurement uncertainty u_x of a result x as a mean of n replicate measurements on p days for a certain MNPs diameter is then estimated as:

$$u_x = \sqrt{\frac{s_r^2}{np} + \frac{s_{day}^2}{p} + s_t^2} \quad (14)$$

For the final evaluation of methods, the worst-case scenario is applied that takes the results of the MNPs with the worst precision/trueness data. If scientifically justified and supported by the validation data, the MNPs could be grouped into categories and uncertainties per type of material could be given.

The expanded uncertainty (U_x) is calculated as shown in Equation 15, where $k = 2$, a coverage factor of 2.

$$U_x = k u_x = 2 u_x \quad (15)$$

III.4.2. Partial method validation

In situations where minor changes are made to a method that has been previously validated, a full validation may not be necessary, depending on the nature of the applied changes. Changes for which a partial validation may be needed include another matrix or species, change in equipment or addition of more equipment (hyphenated techniques). Partial method validation will be uniquely assessed and can range from determining one validation parameter to almost a full method validation.

III.4.3. Software validation

Any custom-made software application should be validated prior to use and undergo re-validation after changes have been made to the underlying equations and/or code.

Software validation must be planned and designed beforehand and should cover the whole functionality of the developed application in question. If possible, only validated data sets with known and documented results should be used. Depending on the application, a meaningful test design may focus on (whatever is most useful):

- inspection and structural testing
- repeated input of test data (at least 5 data sets including the extreme values of the application range)
- screening of functionalities
- separate validation of independent modules

Validation should be carried out not by the software author but by a competent second person. After validation, a report is compiled. This report contains:

- name of the software and revision number;
short description including history, application, scope and limitations;
if applicable, instructions for use, special information;
particular hardware requirements;

- software requirements (e.g. operating system);
- detailed description of the software specifying its functionality and structure (e.g. by printing the source-code or, in the case of Excel files, printing the sheet with the equations);
- theoretical basis of the programme (e.g. explanations of the source of the equations);
- description of tests and their results performed for validation;
- conclusion with a statement on validation and release.

If appropriate, information related to the installation and performance test, user training and further proceeding, e.g. password handling, review requirements, etc., should be provided.

III.4.4. Reporting validations

A validation report is prepared for every validation, comprising a description of the measurements done, the approach and the evaluations. In particular, it must contain the following headers:

- linearity/calibration curve
- working range
- sensitivity
- LOD/LOQ
- trueness
- selectivity and interferences
- repeatability and intermediate precision
- robustness
- stability of samples
- measurement uncertainty.

These parameters must be justified within the validation plan and report, whenever they were not studied as planned. A concluding statement must be added stating if the performance criteria as defined in the validation plan were met.

III.5. Results Reporting

A report of MNPs analysis must contain all parameters (metadata) of the sample, the sample collection and treatment, and at least a brief description of the analytical method, which includes the method's crucial parameters. Cowger et al.⁶ described very detailed reporting guidelines to increase the reproducibility and comparability of research on MNPs. Three documents/guidelines are available to support the reporting process, which presents the same information with different end-users in mind (detailed document, checklist and Mind Map). Furthermore, the general method groups are defined as:

- Materials,
- Quality Assurance/Quality Control (QA/QC),
- Data reporting,
- Field sampling,

⁶ Cowger, Win, Andy M. Booth, Bonnie M. Hamilton, Clara Thaysen, Sebastian Primpke, Keenan Munno, Amy L. Lusher, et al. n.d. 'Reporting Guidelines to Increase the Reproducibility and Comparability of Research on Microplastics.' <https://doi.org/10.1177/00037028209>

- Sample preparation,
- Identification,
- Categorisation,
- Quantification and
- Toxicology Considerations.

The provided literature describes these groups in detail, so this document will only discuss the analytical aspects of the reporting. In summary, the minimum information MNPs analysis results should provide:

- 1) The **total number of particles in the sample** with a description of the units. The laboratory should report quantitative results only if the results exceed the limit of detection (LOD). Otherwise, results should be presented as < LOD. To calculate the total number of MPs in the sample, subtracting the laboratory blank value of the sample series from the sample results is not recommended. The laboratory should indicate the value of the LOD (concentration) with the results.

If sub-sampling during measurement was performed, the analysed area of the filter (%) or statistical percentage of analysed particles on the total number of particles (%) should be reported. For **the total number of particles on the filter**, use the following formula:

$$C_i = \frac{n_i \times F_n}{N} \quad (16)$$

where C_i is the total number of particles on the filter, n_i is the number of particles counted in the sub-sample, F_n is the total number of subsamples, and N is the number of inspected subsamples. For the determination of the 95% confidence limits, the values for the lower and upper 95% confidence limits, λ_L and λ_U , can be obtained from Poisson distribution (Table 3), by converting these values into numerical particle concentrations using the equations:

$$C_i^L = \frac{\lambda_L \times F_N}{N} \quad (17)$$

and

$$C_i^U = \frac{\lambda_U \times F_N}{N} \quad (18)$$

where C_i^L and C_i^U are the lower and upper limit of the 95% confidence interval, respectively.

- 2) The **LOD value(s)**. The LOD may be different for different size classes of particles. While, in general, the LOD may be expressed as the undifferentiated sum of all polymers, polymer-specific LODs may be more advisable for detailed scientific studies.

- 3) The **size dimensions** (e.g., μm , Feret minimum or maximum). **The LOD of particle size.** In terms of spectroscopic methods (e.g. μFTIR and μRaman), the latter may depend on the pore size of the filter. Particles that are smaller than the filter pores can be found on a filter if deposited between pores. The proportion of such particles retained is unknown, and thus, their number is not representative of the sample.
- 4) A description of **the quantification technique** (e.g. optical counting, FPA FT-IR) and image analyses used for counting and sizing of MNPs.
- 5) A description of the **identification technique**. Further, a distinction can be made in the visual identification of particles using certain magnification and image settings and image processing, as well as chemical identification aiming to identify the chemical composition of the MP. For the latter, techniques like μFTIR , μRaman , pyrolysis gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (Py-GCMS) or thermal extraction-desorption gas mass spectrometry (TED-GCMS) may be used. In those cases, describe the data acquisition parameters.
- 6) Description of **sample treatment**, report on aspects of sample homogenisation, sample size, fluorescent dyes used to stain MP, applied digestion techniques (digestion solution composition, temperature and duration), density separation techniques and filtration (filter composition, porosity and diameter).
- 7) Description of **quality assurance and quality control**, report on the number of replicates, the LOD, blank controls, positive controls, contamination mitigation and, if available for the method used, method validation aspects such as recovery, repeatability, reproducibility and measurement uncertainty.

Within the PlasticsFatE project WP2, an **Excel template** was prepared to streamline reporting. The template consists of two Excel tabs: one for reporting results from single-detector μFTIR analyses and another for focal plane array (FPA) FTIR analyses. The template allows users to provide detailed information about the samples (e.g., sample ID, technical or experimental replicates), sample details (e.g., matrix type and QC sample information), sample preparation, and method characteristics. Results should be reported at the level of individual particles, considering the multidimensional nature of the data (e.g., concentration, shape, colour, etc.). Each individual result must be properly assigned to the corresponding sample ID.

Table 3. Upper and lower limits of the Poissonian 95% confidence interval of a count.

Particle count	Lower λ_L	Upper λ_U	Particle count	Lower λ_L	Upper λ_U	Particle count	Lower λ_L	Upper λ_U
0	0	3.689	46	33.678	61.358	92	74.164	112.83
1	0.025	5.572	47	34.534	62.501	93	75.061	113.94
2	0.242	7.225	48	35.392	63.642	94	75.959	115.04
3	0.619	8.767	49	36.251	64.781	95	76.858	116.14
4	1.090	10.242	50	37.112	65.919	96	77.757	117.24
5	1.624	11.669	51	37.973	67.056	97	78.657	118.34
6	2.202	13.060	52	38.837	68.192	98	79.557	119.44
7	2.814	14.423	53	39.701	69.326	99	80.458	120.53
8	3.454	15.674	54	40.567	70.459	100	81.360	121.66
9	4.115	17.085	55	41.433	71.591	110	90.400	132.61
10	4.795	18.391	56	42.301	72.721	120	99.490	143.52
11	5.491	19.683	57	43.171	73.851	130	108.61	154.39
12	6.201	20.962	58	44.041	74.979	140	117.77	165.23
13	6.922	22.231	59	44.912	76.106	150	126.96	176.04
14	7.654	23.490	60	45.785	77.232	160	136.17	186.83
15	8.396	24.741	61	46.658	78.357	170	145.41	197.59
16	9.146	25.983	62	47.533	79.482	180	154.66	208.33
17	9.904	27.219	63	48.409	80.605	190	163.94	219.05
18	10.668	28.448	64	49.286	81.727	200	173.24	229.75
19	11.440	29.671	65	50.164	82.848	210	182.56	240.43
20	12.217	30.889	66	51.042	83.969	220	191.89	251.10
21	13.000	32.101	67	51.922	85.088	230	201.24	261.75
22	13.788	33.309	68	52.803	86.207	240	210.60	272.39
23	14.581	34.512	69	53.685	87.324	250	219.97	283.01
24	15.378	35.711	70	54.567	88.441	260	229.36	293.62
25	16.178	36.905	71	55.451	89.557	270	238.75	304.23
26	16.983	38.097	72	56.335	90.673	280	248.16	314.82
27	17.793	39.284	73	57.220	91.787	290	257.58	325.39
28	18.606	40.468	74	58.106	92.901	300	267.01	335.96
29	19.422	41.649	75	58.993	94.014	310	276.45	346.52
30	20.241	42.827	76	59.880	95.126	320	285.90	357.08
31	21.063	44.002	77	60.768	96.237	330	295.36	367.62
32	21.888	45.175	78	61.657	97.348	340	304.82	378.15
33	22.715	46.345	79	62.547	98.458	350	314.29	388.68
34	23.545	47.512	80	63.437	99.567	360	323.77	399.20
35	24.378	48.677	81	64.328	100.68	370	333.26	409.71
36	25.213	49.840	82	65.219	101.79	380	342.75	420.22
37	26.050	51.000	83	66.111	102.90	390	352.25	430.72
38	26.890	52.158	84	67.003	104.00	400	361.76	441.21
39	27.732	53.315	85	67.897	105.11	410	371.27	451.89
40	28.575	54.469	86	68.790	106.21	420	380.79	462.18
41	29.421	55.622	87	69.684	107.32	430	390.32	472.65
42	30.269	56.772	88	70.579	108.42	440	399.85	483.12
43	31.119	57.921	89	71.474	109.53	450	409.38	493.58
44	31.970	59.068	90	72.370	110.63	460	418.92	504.04
45	32.823	60.124	91	73.267	111.73	470	428.47	514.50